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TERF1 repression as a component of the TE differentiation signature in human iPS cells suggests differences in telomerase dynamics between pluripotent stem cells and the TE.

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We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here identification of TERF1 as a cooperating factor in lineage commitment embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.